

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF FORMING FAMILISTIC COMPETENCE IN BOYS.

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Annotation: *This article: In boys, they consider familistic competence, universal human values, household skills, reasonable order, economic education, and the desire for innovation to be important.*

Key words: *boys, declines, crises, familistic, family values, co-retention, care, moral standards.*

Nowadays, education of familistic competence and universal human values in boys is of great importance. It should be remembered that this situation is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood. At this stage, the psychological and physical development of children is very accelerated. Adolescence is from 11-12 years old, including 14-15 years old, and in some children, the transition to this period can begin mainly from the 5th grade. Adolescence period has its own It is distinguished by imitability, non-formation of an important point of view, courage, masculinity, tact, emotionality. A teenager begins to be interested in various things in life. The desire for new things increases. His inner world is enriched, his character is formed, opposite oppositions arise. Therefore, he looks at some restrictions differently. This period of the child's development is called "complex", "important", "difficult" period. Parents and young teachers who do not yet have sufficient experience in the field of educational work, as well as the necessary knowledge about the age and individual characteristics of children of adolescent age, usually think that raising teenagers is too complicated. But nowadays, the unique laws, features, opportunities, complex mechanisms of expression and emergence of behavior motives of teenagers are known to science. This is characteristic of teenagers. Therefore, it is necessary to pay careful attention to teenage boys and girls, and changes occur in children during this period. These are physiological, biological and psychological. In order to form familistic comretention in adolescent boys, it is first necessary to form this comretention in teachers, because adolescent boys spend most of the day with teachers in general education schools. In the professional activity of teachers who are involved in the formation of schoolchildren's attitude to family values, family competence has an important aspect of professional-edagogical competence in improving the teacher's skills. The formation of family competence in teachers includes:

- understanding the blind functional and blind side of family life;
- the teacher's understanding of the universal value and personal importance of family, family life;

- to have moral standards (respect for parents' feelings, manners, etc.) and professional competences for educating young students in relation to family values.

- to have personal qualities necessary to build their own family life and organize constructive cooperation with students' families based on the technologies of working with different types of families;

- family relations, household skills, culture, communication skills with relatives and close people;

- The system of knowledge about the activities of the family, its creation, implementation of family upbringing of children, ways of constructive interaction with the student's family during its development;

- In order to form familistic comretention in teenage boys, teachers are required to:

-Subjective-personal experience in the development and implementation of models for effective resolution of family life problems, preparation of schoolchildren for family life and psychological-edagogical education of parents;

-Readiness for continuous self-development of family qualities, self-improvement of family relationships, self-improvement in the field of social partnership with parents of students to create a person-oriented educational environment. self-discipline.

The process of education and upbringing of boys is carried out in the closest environment of the child, that is, in the family, parents, older relatives, children, and their friends create an information space where the teenager grows. Through this he enters the society. The principle of skilful use of the demand for respect and humane treatment of children. The main thing is to establish a reasonable order of children's life and behavior in the family, reasonable forms of their relations with other family members. The process goes through education - formation of habits, skills, character traits - transfer of knowledge. Instruct children in the daily routine, including work, study together with rest, how to keep their belongings and work place in order, forming appropriate habits of positive behavior. The next important criterion for the formation of tolerant relations in the family is the creation of a working environment and the development of work skills in children.

The family should be organized according to the type of work team, in which teenage boys will contribute to the creation of material well-being and will be able to measure their needs with material wealth. The best means of encouraging children to work in the family, it looked at the ability of parents to set work tasks, give work instructions, as well as carry out planned work together. At the same time, parents should not forget that people are always trying to please in order not to force children to work. The inability of some parents to expand the field of application of children's forces in practical matters leads to the fact that they do not learn to value work and develop a dependent mood in themselves. Teaching children to work from a young age forms hard work in them, which is one of the important qualities of a good family head.

A.S. Makarenko listed more than 20 types of child labor in the family. They consist of:

Children should make their beds, keep tables and work places in order, clean clothes and linen, take care of flowers, put magazines and newspapers in a certain place, look after siblings and brothers, father - to help mothers clean the apartment, prepare food, and so on.

According to the classification of comretentions accepted by theorists of blindness, they are divided into general and professional. Instrumental comretentions are formed in adolescence. The main ones are cognitive. Thinking is the ability to use ideas and knowledge. Language skills are formed faster in the process of communication, especially in children. The first skills of preschool children are communicative. Not only teachers, but also parents take care that children's questions do not remain unanswered.

In the family, practical qualities such as prudence and thrift are brought up. Means of economic education are stories, games, reading literature, interpreting pictures, watching cartoons, proverbs. There are also non-traditional methods of economic education in the family. For example, a seven-year-old boy "worked".

He was paid a steering wheel for making buttons. A teenage boy realized that the work was not easy, steering wheels were expensive. Tens of years have passed, but the tenacity, hard work, and patience that began at that time have helped him. has been a companion throughout his life. The most important thing in the economic upbringing of children is a respectful attitude

The main criterion in the economy is the personal example of family members in raising a teenage child. Important conversations on the way to children, organization of personal space for the child - his desk, room, play corner, choice of attitude to the child's mistakes and reactions to them. It is even possible to organize a competition between the child and himself. Fathers play an important role in the formation of familistic comretention in adolescent boys. Whether we like it or not, the bird does what it sees in the nest. For the boy, the father is a role model in the family. That's why parents should pay attention to their actions in the family with their children. Adolescence is a period full of contradictions. Some scientists call it the period of "declines" and "crises". The reason is that such crisis situations occur in the psyche of a teenager that, on the one hand, he wants to solve this crisis himself, on the other hand, he does not have the opportunity, strength and intelligence to solve it himself.

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